

A Lightweight Design Approach to An Atmospheric Re-entry Vehicle

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Abstract

A phenol CFRP ablator of a two-layer type that can simultaneously meet both the thermal protection requirement and the heat discharge requirement for a reentry capsule was developed. It also satisfies the strength requirement even if it is completely carbonized.

Since the critical stress for the heat shield system using this two-layer type phenol CFRP is the thermal stress during the capsule's re-entry to the earth's atmosphere, the thickness and the mechanical properties of the constituent materials were optimized using an ablation analysis code with experimental approach.

A new heat insulator (called a "thermal anchor") containing metal foil can meet the heat discharge requirement on orbit to suitable value that also satisfies the thermal insulation requirement in the re-entry phase. The re-entry capsule which adopts the two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator and the new "thermal anchor" insulator can make the heat shield system much lighter as compared with that by the conventional design technique.

KEYWORDS: re-entry vehicle, heat shield, CFRP, porous insulator, lightweight

1. Introduction

Manufacturing large single crystals, curative medicine by utilizing micro gravity environment on orbit and collecting substance of an asteroid surface are the examples of the purpose of space development activity. To recover these materials, reentry vehicles such as the space shuttle and reentry capsules are needed.

Such re-entry vehicles suffer exposure to aerodynamic heating environment during their return to the earth. Therefore, it is necessary to cover their outer wall of the re-entry vehicle with a heat shield system in order to prevent permeation of the aerodynamic heating into them. The heat shield system for a re-entry capsule that consists of heat shield material and internal insulator should have the function to endure the high surface temperature by the aerodynamic heating and to keep the temperature of the internal structure and equipment within the allowable level. The outline such a heat shield system is shown in Fig. 1. Heat shield material must satisfy the requirement of excellent performance such as high specific strength as well as high specific stiffness: it must have high resistance to the shear load generated by the high-speed air flow. The aerodynamic heating rate of a re-entry vehicle which returns to the earth from the space is high; in the case of return from the low earth orbit of which orbital velocity of 7.8 km/s, the value is several MW/m², and in the case of return from the moon orbit at a velocity of about 12km/s, the value is 10 MW/m² or even more. The heat shield material so-called ablator fully withstands this severe aerodynamic heating. The ablator is pyrolyzed and carbonized by aerodynamic heating. The ablator surface is cooled by endothermic reaction, such as dissolution of the ablator. Moreover, the pyrolysis gas which is generated from the ablator surface reduces the aerodynamic heating by being diffused from the vehicle surface. CFRP (carbon- fiber-reinforced plastic) and GFRP (glass-fiber-reinforced plastic) and so on are typical ablators which have had good track records in the re-entry vehicles used. Compared with GFRP, CFRP

has a great advantage that it can be used in a wide range of heating conditions including severe heating environment and that the thermal reaction of CFRP on the surface material is simple compared with that of GFRP and it is easier to predict both CFRP surface temperature and CFRP recession.

In this paper, a lightweight design technique for the re-entry capsule using CFRP ablator is summarized. An epoch-making heat shield system which can drastically make the re-entry capsule light s described.

Fig. 1. Outline of a heat shield system using the two-layer type phenol CFRP

2. Design Requirements for a Re-entry Capsule

The re-entry capsule is housed in the fairing of the rocket and is carried into space. For this reason, the size of the re-entry capsule must be such that it can be encapsulated easily in the rocket fairing. The space experiment equipment and guidance and control equipment are also installed in the re-entry capsule. Therefore, the requirements for both the rocket fairing and the internal equipment limit the thickness of the heat shield system.

Moreover, since there is also a limit to the transportation capacity of the rocket, the re-entry capsule must satisfy severe weight requirement.

The main function of the heat shield system of the re-entry capsule is to endure the severe flight environments such as high aerodynamic heating, high dynamic pressure, and large enthalpy to protect the capsule mechanically and thermally.

As for the heat shield system, in addition to the thermal protection requirement, a still severer design requirement must be met. In the case of re-entry capsule, the heat shield system needs to perform heat discharge heat on orbit from the equipment housed in the capsule. That is to say, the heat shield system design must provide an optimal solution to the conflicting design requirements (the orbit heat discharge requirement, the re-entry thermal protection and the heat insulation requirement).

The main requirements for the heat shield system design include the following.

- a) On orbit condition and re-entry initial condition
 - * Heat discharge requirement on orbit
 - * Initial temperature
- b) Requirements during re-entry
 - * Aerodynamic heating, aerodynamic loading and enthalpy
 - * Surface recession thickness restrictions, shell temperature at landing
- c) Structure weight and heat shield system weight
- d) Requirement for the outside and inside shape, and restriction on heat shield system thickness

3. Lightweight Design Technique

One of the design techniques that can meet the design requirements shown in Chapter 2 is to make the ablator as thin as possible. The ablator will be pyrolyzed if material surface is heated, and a carbonized layer of low

density will be formed. The strength of this carbonized layer is generally low compared with virgin material. Therefore, one of the design techniques now in use is to leave a virgin material layer of high strength. Although the heat shield system then becomes heavy, this technique can satisfy the strength requirement. However, if all the carbonized ablator is used as a structural member, the thickness of the heat shield system will decrease. An example of the heat shield system which acts as carbonized ablator during re-entry, is shown in Fig. 1. This heat shield material is two-layer type ablator made of phenol CFRP. The two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator can be divided into a surface heat shield layer and a back heat shield layer. The surface heat shield layer is made by using a technique that chopped prepreg pieces are compressed at high temperature. The surface layer, which mainly functions as a heat shield layer, does not cause de-lamination and has a property to overcome a shear load. The back heat shield layer is made of laminated prepreg and mainly functions as a structural member even if it is completely carbonized. The use of two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator is an epoch-making concept that can attain lighter weight, compared with the heat shield system using the conventional phenol CFRP, which surely leaves the non-pyrolyzed layer (virgin material layer) to function as a structural member. The two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator was adopted for use in the REM (Re-entry Module) capsule of the USERS (Unmanned Space Experiment Recovery System) space vehicle⁽¹⁾.

The design of the heat shield system using the two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator can be classified into the following two.

- (1) heat shield design, and
- (2) ablator strength design

3-1 Heat shield design ⁽²⁾

It is important to design the ablator as thin as possible, which can make a drastically light heat shield system possible. The structural temperature must be maintained with this ablator thickness within the allowable range. In order to make the ablator thin, there is the following technique. In order to make thickness of Phenol CFRP as thin as possible, it is necessary to predict the temperature of the surface and the inside as correctly as possible. The measured surface temperature and inside temperature are shown in Fig.2 and Fig. 3. Figures 2 and 3 also show the calculated temperature using an ablation analysis code. It is understood that calculated value agrees with these measured data. When this ablation analysis code is used for temperature prediction, it is possible to set up the optimal thickness of the two-layer type Phenol CFRP ablator.

Fig. 2. Surface temperature of phenol CFRP Fig. 3. In-depth temperature history of phenol CFRP

However, the recession prediction of the phenol CFRP is not easy so that the thermo-chemical reaction is complicated. The recession prediction for the phenol CFRP, a graphite material, and a carbon-carbon material and so on is shown in Eq. 1 ⁽³⁾. Where p_e is pressure at stagnation (Pa) and R_B is vehicle radius at the stagnation point (m). Eq. 1 can predict recession (mass fraction on heat shield material surface) in the following three

thermo-chemical reaction regions. When surface temperature is less than approximately 1500 K, it is in the “rate-controlled oxidation” region. In this region, surface recession occurs by oxidation reaction in its boundary layer. If surface temperature went up higher than approximately 3000K, it is in the “sublimation” region. It means the surface sublimates and the amount of recession increases according to an exponential function. When surface temperature is between from approximately 1500 K to approximately 3000 K, it is in the “diffusion-controlled oxidation” region. It means all the oxygen diffusing through the boundary layer is consumed in the reaction of the surface. In the diffusion-controlled oxidation region, the amount of recession does not depend only on pressure.

$$\dot{m} = \sqrt{\frac{p_e}{R_B} \frac{1.18 \times 10^5 e^{\frac{22140}{T_w}}}{\sqrt{\frac{30.5}{R_B} + 4.85 \times 10^{15} \times \left(\frac{e^{\frac{22140}{T_w}}}{1 + 3.48 \times 10^8 p_e e^{\frac{61700}{T_w}}} \right)}}}} \quad (1)$$

Detra-Kemp-Riddell aerodynamic heating estimation method is shown in Eq. 2. This equation is a correlation equation based on experimental data of the axis symmetrical objects. It is often used for the aerodynamic heating rate estimation of the re-entry vehicles.

$$q_e = \frac{1.108 \times 10^8}{R_B^{0.5}} \left[\frac{\rho_\infty}{\rho_{SL}} \right]^{0.5} \left[\frac{V_e}{V_{re}} \right]^{3.15} \left[\frac{(h_e - h_w)}{(h_e - h_{w300})} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where q_e is the aerodynamic heating rate at stagnation point (W/m^2). ρ_∞ is the free stream air density (kg/m^3), ρ_{SL} is the air density at sea level (kg/m^3). V_e is the velocity at stagnation (m/sec), V_{re} is fixed as 7925 (m/sec). h_e is the enthalpy of air at stagnation (J/kg), h_w is the enthalpy on the vehicle surface (J/kg), h_{300} is the enthalpy of air in 300 K (J/kg). Eq. 2 shows that q_e is dependent on velocity, pressure ($\approx \rho^{0.5} v^2$) and enthalpy. From Eq. 1, the recession is under the influence of the surface temperature, and the surface temperature is influenced the aerodynamic heating rate. The aerodynamic heating rate is not independent only of the pressure. Therefore, the amount of recession is not influenced only by the pressure. For example, when R_B set to 0.5 (m) constant and q_e set to 2.0 (MW/m^2) constant, the stagnation point enthalpy h_e is 12 (MJ/kg) when the stagnation point pressure p_e is 0.1 (MPa), and h_e is 7 (MJ/kg) when p_e is 0.7 (MPa). Therefore, it is necessary to predict recession using aerodynamic heating rate and enthalpy. Eq. 3 is an equation can be calculated a normalized mass flux rate B'_c which consists of mass flux \dot{m} (kg/sec), aerodynamic heating rate q_e , enthalpy at stagnation h_e and blowing factor ϕ ⁽⁴⁾. Blowing factor ϕ is the value of aerodynamic heating rate reduction by pyrolysis gas and (or) sublimation gas. ϕ is set to approximately 0.9 in this paper.

$$B'_c = \frac{\dot{m}}{(q_e / h_e) \phi} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the normalized ablation rates B^*c for the carbonic material in air and its surface temperature. The experimental results are also shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Relation between the normalized ablation rate B^*c and the surface temperature in air

In the range of surface temperature from about 1500K to about 3000K, this normalized ablation rates B^*c in air keeps a fixed value (approximately 0.17) due to the action of complete CO formation ($C+O \rightarrow CO$). Fig.5 shows good agreement between predicted value and measured value. By using this B^*c theory, the recession of the two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator can be predicted with high accuracy.

3-2 Ablator strength design ⁽⁵⁾

Even if the ablator is completely carbonized, the ablator thickness, which is determined as in Section 3-1, must have a value that can endure the aerodynamic load and the thermal load during re-entry. The sources of the stress generated in the heat shield system are the aerodynamic load and the thermal load due to the aerodynamic heating. In the case of the REM capsule, the thermal stress accounts for a large part of the total stress compared with the stress due to the aerodynamic load. The mechanical properties, which affect the thermal stress generated between two components (like that between the two layers of two-layer type phenol CFRP), are the coefficient of thermal expansion, Young's modulus, and Poisson's ratio ⁽⁶⁾. Difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion, Young's modulus, and the temperature distribution determine the magnitude and the location of thermal stress ⁽⁵⁾. The theoretical value of the thermal stress generated between two materials is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Thermal stress generated into two materials in the case of being different in mechanical properties

Two materials in Fig. 5 differ in the values of mechanical properties. The thermal-stress distribution inside is

controllable by adjusting the thickness ratio of the surface and the back material. Moreover, the thermal stress between two materials can be adjusted also with the ratio of Young's modulus. Furthermore, the details are explained. The back ablator's stress mainly consists of the induced stress by the back ablator's plastic stress and the thermal stress occurring in the back ablator itself. Induced stress by the back ablator which made of the chopped prepreg pieces has upper limit, because the chopped cloth ablator is in plastic stress range (Plastic stress has upper limit.). Therefore, the induced stress by the chopped cloth does not exceed the upper limit, even if the temperature rises furthermore. The stress distribution in the back ablator is influenced to the temperature distribution and the thermal expansion coefficient and the plastic stress, because the back ablator is in plastic range. The thermal stress occurring in the back ablator itself is also influenced to the temperature distribution, the thermal expansion coefficient and the young modulus, because the back ablator is in elastic range.

On the other hand, the surface ablator causes the thermo-chemical recession by aerodynamic heating. Thus, the optimal thickness of the surface ablator and that of the back ablator can be determined from the mechanical properties and the amount of recession. Ideally, the validity of the thickness of the ablator thus determined and the method of nonlinear stress analysis are evaluated by ground tests. There are two main ground tests. One is to clarify the relation of the deformation of carbonized ablator and the temperature in high-temperature, nonlinear region. The other is to ensure that the breaking load of carbonized ablator is beyond the required value in the critical temperature, nonlinear region. However, since it is difficult to simulate completely the aerodynamic heating environment during re-entry by ground tests, the nonlinear stress analysis whose method is verified by the two ground tests mentioned above is performed. An example of ablator strength analysis is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Example of stress distribution due to thermal stress and aerodynamic load (temperature dependency of all mechanical properties has not overridden)

This analysis is an example of the stress distribution on the back-face of the two-layer ablator of the vehicle at the time of exposure to aerodynamic heating and the aerodynamic load. The mechanical properties used for the calculation of Fig. 6 are considered to be temperature-dependent. From this stress analysis, whether it is a suitable thickness value of the ablator or not can be judged. When it is expected that the ablator which has temporarily the thickness determined in section 3-1 cannot satisfy the requirement for strength, the two-layer type phenol CFRP must be thickened. In this case, it is necessary to ensure that the improved two-layer type phenol CFRP can satisfy the thermal protection requirement and the heat discharge requirement.

On the other hand, the two-layer type phenol CFRP ablator surface receives a shear-load by friction with air during re-entry. The shear-load of the material surface is calculable by Eq. 4.

$$\tau = \frac{q_s V_s}{h_s} \quad (4)$$

Where τ is the shear-load (N/m^2), q_s is the cold wall heat flux rate at the surface (MW/m^2), h_s is the stream

enthalpy (MJ/kg), V_s is the stream velocity at the surface (m/sec).

In the case of the REM capsule, the maximum shear-load can be estimated approximately 300 (N/m²). The shear load of approximately 400 (N/m²) was applied to the two-layer type phenol CFRP material using the arc-heating testing facility. The heated surfaces of all test models were inspected. No faults were found on the surface.

4 Thermal control design

In order to discharge heat on orbit passively, it is necessary to set the thermal conductance (SI units: W/m²/K) of the heat shield system at a suitable value. The material with overwhelmingly low thermal conductivity (SI units: W/m/K) is insulator, which is a component material of the heat shield system. Thus, the thermal conductance of the heat shield system is governed by the thermal conductivity of the insulator used. Increasing the thermal conductivity of the insulator means allowing more permeation of aerodynamic heating. Thus, the thermal conductivity as well as the thickness of the insulator that can satisfy simultaneously the heat discharge requirement on orbit and the heat insulation requirement during re-entry is required. The USERS REM has adopted a new insulator that is called "thermal anchor". The concept of the "thermal anchor" type insulator is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. New insulator concept, which is called "Thermal Anchor"

This new insulator is a porous insulator with aluminum foil inserted in it. The thermal conductivity of the insulator can be controlled by adjusting the thickness and the distance (referred to as "d" in Fig. 9) between the sheets of foil. The effective thermal conductivity of the "thermal anchor" can be estimated from the thermal conductivity and the area ratio (namely, distance d) of the heat insulator and the aluminum alloy foil. The relation between the area ratio of the aluminum alloy foil and the effective thermal conductivity is shown in Fig 8. It is found that if the area ratio of the aluminum alloy is changed, the effective thermal conductivity of the heat insulator can be efficiently controlled. The validity of the effective thermal conductance thus determined is mainly evaluated by ground tests. However, it is difficult to simulate all orbit temperature conditions completely by ground tests. For this reason, the validity of the set point of thermal conductance is also evaluated by analysis. The validity of the thermal mathematical model used for analysis is evaluated by tests, and when the analysis results and the test results are not in agreement, the heat mathematical model is improved.

Fig. 8. Relation between the area ratio of metal foil and the effective thermal conductivity of “ Thermal Anchor”

5. Lightweight Heat Shield System

At a station near stagnation point on the REM capsule, the analysis on strength was carried out separately and showed that the ablator thickness needed to be about 19 mm or more. Further, the thickness of the metal structure was set to be 7.5 mm. This metal structure was made of an aluminum alloy (refer to Fig. 1). It was found that phenol CFRP was pyrolyzed above about 300 degree Centigrade. The material whose back surface temperature becomes about 300 degree Centigrade or more is accordingly called in this paper "completely carbonized ablator".

When the ablator back temperature is required to be maintained for sufficient strength, the required temperature is 250 degree Centigrade (refer to Fig. 9), and the ablator thickness should be about 31 mm. When the thermal conductance is required to be more than 7 W/m²/K, the corresponding thickness of the insulator is about 5 mm or less. Then, the total mass (the metal structure mass added to the heat shield system mass) can be estimated to be about 68 kg/m². (Refer to Fig. 10.) Although the thickness of heat insulator has greatly affects its thermal conductance, its total mass does not affect. In all carbonization designs, the temperature on the back of the ablator does not serve as a restricting condition of fundamental design. The ablator thickness from the viewpoint of strength should be 19 mm or more. From Fig. 10, it is found that heat insulator whose thickness is about 6 mm and ablator whose thickness is 19 mm can satisfy the required value of 7 W/m² / K of thermal conductance. The total mass under these conditions is 50 kg/m².

Fig. 9. Relation between the two-layer type phenol CFRP thickness and the back surface maximum temperature

Figure 11 shows the relation between the ablator thickness and total mass ratio, the total mass ratio is assumed to be 1.0 when the ablator thickness is 31 mm. From Fig. 11, when the ablator thickness is 19 mm, the total mass ratio is 0.74. As compared with the design that leaves a non-pyrolyzed layer (virgin layer), about 25% or more of weight reduction is possible by all carbonization designs. As mentioned above, when all the carbonization design methods are adopted, drastic weight reduction of the re-entry capsule will be possible. The relation between two-layer type phenol CFRP thickness and the maximum temperature of the metal structure is shown in Fig. 12. Although all carbonization designs are the design technique, which can make ablator thin, this design's metal structure temperature goes up as compared with the design that leaves a non-pyrolyzed layer (virgin layer). It is also important to carry out in all carbonization designs, so that metal structure temperature will not exceed a permissible temperature.

Fig. 10. Relation between the two-layer type phenol CFRP thickness, and whole mass and heat conductance

Fig. 11. Relation between the two-layer type phenol CFRP thickness and whole mass ratio

Fig. 12. Relation between the two-layer type phenol CFRP thickness and maximum structure temperature

Conclusions

Important items in performing the heat shield system design of the re-entry capsule are the following:

- (1) heat shield design,
- (2) thermal control design, and
- (3) ablator strength design.

Effective integration of these separate technologies enables the mass minimization design of the re-entry capsule. There is a method of mass minimization design of the re-entry capsule which uses two-layer type phenol CFRP. If the two-layer type phenol CFRP is used, as compared with the conventional heat shield design technique, the results of an example design showed that it is possible to reduce the weight drastically, and this technique can be expected to contribute greatly to an effective use of the launch capacity of many future rockets.

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